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CONFLICT MANAGEMENT IN MODERN CONDITIONS OF ECONOMIC ACTIVITY

КОНФЛІКТ МЕНЕДЖМЕНТ У СУЧАСНИХ УМОВАХ ЕКОНОМІЧНОЇ ДІЯЛЬНОСТІ

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У статті розглянуті причини та наслідки конфліктів всередині команди, шляхи їх розв'язання і управління ними, визначено основні типи конфліктів, їх переваги і недоліки, досліджено варіанти розвитку і впливу на рівень продуктивності групи. Також запропоновано ряд алгоритмів дій в конфліктній ситуації, проаналізовано можливі ролі лідера команди і стилі конфлікту. Розглянуто етичні і психологічні норми взаємодії учасників команди в умовах віддаленої роботи і запропоновано реальні техніки і правила, що допоможуть досягнути гармонійної роботи в дистанційному режимі, адже конфлікт може призвести до знаходження нових ідей і механізмів вирішення організаційних проблем, отже стимулювати інновації та позитивні зміни. Актуальність вирішення даної наукової проблеми полягає в тому, що діагностика конфліктів дозволить менеджменту розробити набір превентивних заходів, ефективних у разі недопущення або згладжування конфліктних ситуацій.

Ключові слова: конфлікт, адміністративне управління, командна робота, менеджмент, управлінські конфлікти, дистанційна робота, суперечка, лідер, конструктивний конфлікт

Zamlynskiy V.A., Shardakova A.D, Adil Mohamed Abdalla Sultan Al Ali. Conflict management in modern conditions of economic activity. Review article.

The article discusses the causes and consequences of conflicts within the team, ways to resolve and manage them. The main types of conflicts, their advantages and disadvantages are identified, the options of development and impact on the level of group productivity are investigated. A number of algorithms for action in a conflict situation are also proposed, depending on the position held. Possible roles of team leader and conflict styles are analyzed. Ethical and psychological norms of team members' interaction in remote work are considered and real techniques and rules are offered to help achieve harmonious work remotely, because conflict can lead to finding new ideas and mechanisms for solving organizational problems, thus stimulating innovation and positive change. The urgency of solving this scientific problem is that the diagnosis of conflicts will allow management to develop a set of preventive measures that are effective in preventing or smoothing out conflict situations.

Keywords: conflict, administrative management, teamwork, management, managerial conflicts, remote work, dispute, leader, constructive conflict

In today's constantly changing modern business environment, business managers are actively expanding the range of company operations through successful communications and long-term relationships that they develop between two, three or more parties, as well as within the organization. Hundreds of thousands of entrepreneurs and employees face their interests every day. Successful relations and coordinated work can be destroyed by inefficient negotiation and using false approaches to conflict management. The failures may also be the result of misunderstandings and misconceptions about the parties positions and interests.

Many people consider conflict to be something dangerous and undesirable, something that should be avoided at any sacrifice. However, conflicts of interest are an integral part of human relations. Even the history of mankind is an endless tale of conflicts and constant struggle. At the present stage of transition to market relations, conflicts are nowhere more active than in the business sector. Conflicts are formed between firms, companies, associations, within one organization and so on. Conflicts sometimes occur in any team, even the most cohesive. Especially if the activities of the organization are related to creativity, digital or advertising. An experienced leader should not only be able to resolve the conflict, but also turn it in the right direction and benefit the company. This is why it is necessary to know how to recognize the conflict in the early stages, how to work with it in the conditions of offline and remote work and what consequences to expect if

not treated wisely and vice versa – if one acts competently, as discussed in the article.

Analysis of recent research and publications

The problem of conflicts was given attention in many areas, especially in political studies: the elite theory (W. Pareto, R. Mosca), political groups (A. Bentley), the political stability theory (S. Lipset, D. Sanders, etc.), ethnopolitical theories and others. Conflicts were considered in psychology: S. Freud, K.-G. Jung, E. Bern, K. Levin. The studies of Adler and Rodman, Putnam and Wilson, Marilyn Kelly, Bolton, Alexeyev have been considered in the work. O. Kozlova and V. Kozlov (2020) considered the issue of conflicts online. The impact of a global pandemic on the conflict studies development was studied by Baldwin and Freeman (2021).

Possible ways of team conflicts development are revealed in different scenarios, which differ in the algorithms nature of action chosen by managers and employees, as well as the methodology of personnel selection and impact on staff. All of these works under consideration have in common – conflict – it is not always bad for the organization, if it is properly managed and maintained in normal concentration.

According to I.S. Alekseytsev's definition conflict is a sudden exacerbation of contradictions (conflict situation) and a collision of two or more participants (persons) while solving a problem (object) that has business or individual significance [1].

Having analyzed the various definitions of conflict, we can name the main features and properties of the conflict:

- Conflict is a clash of the parties;
- The clashes can occur for many reasons;
- Participants are interdependent, the actions of one party affect the actions of the other party and vice versa;
- Each party regards the opponent's actions as hostile;

— The struggle is aimed at achieving the goal by suppressing the opponent.

Conflict is a part of the basic dynamics of human interaction in which people try their best to balance self-care with relationships. When this balance is disturbed, human interaction becomes alienated and destructive. In further words, there has been a crisis in human interaction. The conflict takes away resources, upsets balance, brings psychological and physical discomfort to self-realization and communication, deprives points of support, reduces self-sufficiency, security, survival, and ultimately the quality of interaction with society.

If conflict is expressed in an angry or aggressive manner, it can damage the organization and destroy interpersonal relationships. Emerging contradictions within the organization itself can lead to a conflict situation, and in a team with a strained relationship is much lower productivity, because employees' thoughts are occupied with thoughts and negative emotions, which prevents them from focusing and doing their job well.

However, when properly managed, conflict can be a valuable tool that has an extremely positive impact on the business and personal environment. In an effective solution, a functional conflict can provide an opportunity to learn new details and take part in new interesting thoughts and ideas, achieve deeper understanding and help to improve and strengthen personal and professional relationships.

Whether conflict will be productive and how it will affect the organization as a whole depends on how it will be perceived by the participants and whether it will contribute to the team goals.

Every conflict is based on organizational, production and interpersonal reasons. Conflicts classification by parties and causes is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Conflicts Classification
Source: authors' own development

Conflict in the team arises from several sources. Some conflicts are based on how people behave, some are due to differences over the work of the team. The main causes of conflicts in the organization are:

- different goals and interests: Conflict arise if the team members have competing desires or needs as each person is unique, has his/her own viewpoint, interests, experience, own and collective vision of the development strategy. For example, a fight for

a particular task during team work. The participant who does not receive it may hide the grudge or anger of another. Failure to communicate effectively, to accept a different member of the team, his/her own vision, low level of social responsibility, culture and moral norms can lead to conflict escalation;

- differences in behavioural styles: this includes speech tone, work habits etc.;
- competition for resource. For example, the simultaneous need to use limited equipment or an assistant;
- non-compliance with team standards. Currently, the rules of behaviour are very vague, so it is necessary to bring them up for discussion as often as possible and disseminate them among employees. A very relevant example is the ban on the using telephones at meetings, ignoring this rule is often the cause of conflict;
- uneven labour distribution: when some team members do not invest in work enough, do not contribute or ignore their responsibilities;
- poor communication: in this case, it is no longer about the team. Everyone can have their own goal and different ways of achieving it. As a result, there is a misunderstanding and conflict during the attempt to unite in the final of the work;
- uncertainty about goals and means: lack of precision and clarity can lead people to make their own assumptions, which may not be the same, leading to conflict.

The aim of the article is to analyse how a conflict can both help and damage the team productivity, identify the causes of conflicts within the organization and how to overcome them and manage them. To consider how to use the conflict as a strategy of cooperation and increase the team efficiency. To find the ways to deescalate conflicts both offline and online.

The main part

The following materials were used for effective analysis and research: scientific works, Internet sources, materials on profile and periodic editions. Methods of concretization, analysis, synthesis, abstraction, dialectical method for conflict risk analysis and their impact on team work efficiency were used.

Results. Managing people is a big responsibility first and foremost, and productivity, recruitment, training and conflict management are also important and paramount. A good manager helps to overcome the gap between where the employee is now and where he/she wants to be, aligning it with the company goals, using a wide range of behavioural techniques and techniques that help to achieve the planned set of goals and improve professional performance. These actions require a creative approach, strategic thinking, diagnosis and rational management decisions. The conflicting parties have not yet ended, they need each other and are bargaining to reach a mutually acceptable solution. The leader must understand the conflict dynamics before he/she

can come up with a compromise solution. The desirable result is as follows: both sides of the conflict must win and strengthen their positions, i.e., act on a "win-win" basis.

Conflict is a natural process through which a person or group feels disenchanted in the actions of management, colleagues or subordinates, an unsatisfactory strategy to achieve certain goals, plans or tasks. Managers tend to focus on financial performance, plans implementation, adherence to terms, and conflict aspects of personnel management and conducting "difficult" conversations are considered secondary. The majority is ready to stop the conflict with dismissal, demonstrating the power and necessity of unconditional hearing of other team members. There is a number of problems in the perception of conflict phenomena by companies: evaluating the role of business reputation, corporate culture, social responsibility of participants, which are important elements of the management system of modern organization, and insufficient development of the theoretical component of interaction and interaction of these components requires strengthening of their role in the concept of social responsibility and sustainable development of the enterprise.

Marilyn Kelly in her work [2] identified the following types of conflicts over the person:

- Significant conflicts. These conflicts concern choices in the situation, based on different views of the facts. Another term for designation of such conflicts is "internal conflict";
- Value conflicts are conflicts in which different parties either adhere to completely different values or evaluate the same values in significantly different ways;
- Processes conflicts arise when people disagree on how to achieve goals;
- Misperceptions conflicts of arise when people misinterpret each other's actions or emotions.

These four types of conflicts can interact with each other over time, increasing or decreasing each other's influence. In turn, all the team members can set rules, principles and norms that will help to create a constructive conflict. Teams can see a conflict as a strategy for continuous growth, improvement and development. Recognizing the positive aspects of the conflict and its implementation as part of the team process can increase team productivity. Minor conflicts have the right to exist as they help to identify weaknesses and obstacles to cooperation that can be overcome by changes in behaviour, discussion and acceptance of the other person's viewpoint. It can also help to eliminate minor defects and make better decisions, as it allows to consider the situation from different sides and hear different opinions, so to find a compromise. Conflict resolution can increase team cohesion by involving participants in the discussion of important issues. Team members can feel more valuable when they know they are contributing to something vital to the team success. Conflict can reveal assumptions that can be applied in the current situation, and thus allow the team to agree on a new

course. It can also draw attention to norms that have been developed without the explicit consent of team

members and create an opportunity to approve or reject them.

Table 1. The Main Possible Consequences of the Team Conflict

Positive consequences of a team conflict	Negative consequences of a team conflict
Increase productivity, develop cohesion, and eliminate misunderstandings that have arisen.	Differences caused by hostility between individuals can reduce team cohesion and the ability of team members to work together, resulting in the division of the group.
Shortcomings identification in the mechanism of team interaction and their elimination.	Conflicts can distract a team, require time and effort to resolve, delay tasks, and threaten team goals.
Ideas collision and birth of more creative decisions, change or improvement of used approaches.	Tension and excessive concentration of negative emotions destroy the favourable atmosphere and reduce the satisfaction of team members.
Overcoming conflicts between parties can facilitate collaboration by helping participants adapt to the requirements and needs of others.	In extreme cases, the conflict, if not resolved, can lead to complete inability of the team to function and its dissolution.

Source: authors' own development

Conflict is a natural component of group interaction and can indeed be beneficial if it is accurately identified, controlled and managed. However, the conflict development can also be dangerous, especially if it is initially ignored, postponing the resolution of the incident indefinitely.

Thus, the main possible consequences of the team conflict are presented in Table 1.

Having analyzed the table, we can conclude that there are two options for the conflict development, which is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Conflict Development Options

Source: authors' own development

From the above mentioned it is clear that the constructive (healthy) conflict creation is appropriate and in most cases is a positive phenomenon in the organization.

Conflict development depends on its timely and correct assessment according to the scheme:

- In what sphere has the conflict arisen: in the process of resolving official issues, or in the private relations of employees? First of all, a business conflict is resolved, as personal requires much more emotional and energy costs, to resolve it requires more time and work of its participants.
- What are the reasons, objective or subjective, the conflict is created?
- What it can potentially be: constructive or destructive?
- What is an obstacle to an objective assessment of the conflict situation that has arisen?

Participants and the team leader can follow these recommendations in order to consciously encourage constructive conflicts:

- to identify collisions in the category of goals, not causes;

- to create the atmosphere of trust by increasing mutual influence and information exchange;
- the leader can demonstrate in his example that it is a healthy conflict that stimulates productivity growth. This will help the rest of the team to consider conflict as normal, and even useful, thus, reflecting the fear of expressions;
- the team members can reduce the risk of conflict by setting boundaries in terms of emotional intensity by setting clear rules. For example, the rule is to focus and discuss the subject of the conflict, in no case focusing on the individual.
- minimize negativity and aggression. For example, replace the phrase "I disagree / against" with "I have another vision".

A distinction must be made between conflicts "resolution" and "management". Conflict resolution is aimed at completely resolving differences and conflicts between team members. Conflict management, on the other hand, aims to minimize, and ideally eliminate, the negative impact of conflict on the team environment and performance.

The way the team perceives and experiences conflicts that arise between the participants during the work directly influences whether these conflicts will be resolved and how, and, as a result, the final results of the team work.

Of course, there are many options to influence conflict. But there are three main approaches to conflict resolution: integration, distribution and mediation. A detailed description of these approaches is presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Basic Approaches to Conflict Resolution and Management
 Source: authors' own development

Although all three approaches put an end to active conflict, the situation in the team and its cohesion may suffer if the participants accept the approach as unfair, incorrect, disrespectful or controversial. As a result, there may be hidden or overt indignation, which has every chance of being reborn into a new conflict that could have been avoided.

The mediation approach deserves special attention, because it involves the emergence of a third party. The mediator sees the conflict as a solved problem. The goal is similar to win-win negotiations, where the goal is to satisfy the interests of both parties. Under mediation, the mediator's success in resolving a problem lies in resolving the dispute. In transformative mediation, the mediator's goal is to empower each party and increase long-term recognition of each other, rather than a one-time dispute resolution. There are also disadvantages of mediation. For example, if the parties to the dispute

do not want to participate in the mediation process, it will not work.

In the event of the inevitable occurrence of a destructive conflict, it is necessary to minimize the negative impact on the team. In such a situation, it is necessary to resort to conflict management methods.

The main purpose of conflict management is to promote the positive effects and reduce the negative consequences that disputes can have on the work of the team, not necessarily completely resolving conflict itself. Conflict management is characterized in the development of strategies for conflict behaviour, in the suppression or stimulation of conflicts.

There are three main tactics for conflict management: smoothing, concessions, and avoidance. A detailed description of these approaches is presented in Figure 3.

The approach to conflict management should be chosen based on its source, importance and intensity.

Conflict can completely paralyze the team, or even an entire organization, by becoming dysfunctional and lead to a sharp decline in efficiency or, in the worst case, violence in the workplace.

At the same time, a moderate number of conflicts is considered perfectly healthy and is even a necessary part of the life of the organization.

The impact of too many or too a conflicts affects productivity not for the better. If the conflict level in an organization is too low, productivity is in the low level. If there are too many conflicts, productivity also tends to decline. The team goal is to keep the conflict level at the optimal level, i.e., in the middle (Figure 4).

Figure 4. The Influence of the Conflict Level in the Organization on the Functioning Efficiency
 Source: authors' own development

The middle level is optimal because it determines the organization where healthy discussion of ideas is practiced. The conflict can be especially helpful in the early stages of decision-making because it stimulates new perspectives and allows for a more creative approach. But in the long run, it is necessary to be more careful as this can hinder the implementation of complex tasks.

Personal conflicts are never healthy as they cause aggression, stress and suffering, which in no way help to increase productivity, but only take away strength, time and attention to details. Let's consider the theorists' research, who have identified and presented a number of conflict styles in groups. All three studies include a number of approaches presented in table 2.

Table 2. Individual Conflict Styles in Groups

Putnam and Wilson [4]	Rakhym, Antonioni y Psenychka [6]	Adler and Rodman [3]
Non-conflict	Integration	Unconfident
	Binding	Direct-aggressive
Controlling	Dominant	Passive aggressive
	Avoidance	Indirect communication
Cooperative	Compromise	Claim/Affirmation

Source: authors' own development

The best development is considered to be the last line in table 2 due to the fact that when translating conflict in such styles, the parties disagree with the world and both opponents are satisfied, that is the conflict leads to positive or neutral consequences.

In order to get out of conflict, different algorithms should be followed, depending on where you are: you

are a group leader, and conflict is among the subordinates; you are an employee-participant, the conflict is with your colleague; you are a participant, conflict is with a subordinate, or with the management; you are an organization representative, conflict is with another organization.

Figure 5. A Leader's Basic Roles
 Source: authors' own development

If you are a group leader, and the conflict was formed within the team, then in order to successfully lead the team through the conflict, you would need patience, will power, intelligence and determination. Robert Bolton wrote in his paper [5] that "smart use of power, charisma and using effective communication skills can have a particularly positive effect on the conflict resolution process".

Let's consider the four key roles that a leader can use to deal with the conflict (Figure 5).

It is important that a successful leader must be able to change and combine roles depending on the circumstances.

- a leader as a motivator: just as more than one person is needed to create a conflict, it usually takes more than one person to resolve it. The leader should therefore try to somehow encourage other members of the group to determine the benefits of participating in a productive rather than destructive conflict;
- a leader as a delegator: neither a leader, nor even a leader of a few other people on a small team, can handle all the problems or do all the work of the group. In addition to acknowledging the complete impossibility of taking over all the work of the group, the leader can try to prevent or resolve conflict by acting wisely as a delegate, transferring responsibility for various tasks to other;
- a leader as a "structuralist": paradoxically, but the leader can also overcome conflict by dividing people rather than uniting them. If the team is experiencing an internal conflict that seems to be related to, for example, strong personal differences between two people, the leader may decide to change the team composition in order to reduce their interaction;
- a leader as the propagandist of "constructive deviation": in fact, it is very difficult for those who deviate from nature to influence the group due to the resistance of other people. For this reason, a part of the leader's responsibility can sometimes be to make sure that those who deviate from the course are not overwhelmed by the majority. In other cases, it is the leader who, at least sometimes, takes on the role of the deviant party.

The main prerequisite for the success of conflict is the adequacy of its participants. It is in the case when each party understands that a constructive conflict is a normal part of communication, and a destructive one is only violated, the leader will participate in the conflict only as an intermediary, and the organization will establish a healthy working atmosphere. So, it is necessary to promote environmental communication from the very beginning. This is achieved when:

- the company has signed an agreement that really reflects the formed system of work with the personnel, remuneration and motivation, the official instruction on each direction, the written information on work conditions and work place, etc. in order to familiarize the employee with the real conditions in advance and that on this basis there is no conflict – the contract will serve as a "regulator" in case of tension of the situation;

- personnel evaluation system is transparent;
- mission and values are embedded in adaptation, training and development programs;
- the company regularly conducts the personnel satisfaction surveys;
- the company has a transparent system of internal communications for rapid exchange of information (scheduled team meetings, corporate chat, regular meetings to clarify the strategy);
- personnel dismissal is carried out strictly according to the procedures described in the special provision;
- the company has established clear rules of communication. For example, the rule on constructing "I-statements": to replace expressions like "you are nervous, you have made mistakes..." by statements like "I am angry because this error has led to such consequences: ..." and the rule of criticism by the "sandwich" method: to praise – criticism – completion in a pleasant note.

If you are a direct participant in the conflict, the following recommendations should be followed.

Confidence in complete control of emotions. If the conversation becomes aggressive or overly tense, it is necessary to take a break or postpone it to the time when emotions will not control the situation. It is necessary to follow the algorithm:

- the problem definition. The statement of your needs is respectful and honest, taking into account the needs of the other person involved;
- reporting the problem without blaming the other person (again, we use "self-statements" or "sandwiches");
- active listening. Giving another person the opportunity to speak, while body language is relaxed and not threatened;
- solutions research;
- reply. Actions in accordance with the decision that was agreed. Focus on maintaining positive working relationships. Sometimes it is advisable to involve the manager.

If conflict arose with the head, it is not a career suicide. In fact, confident managers want to have employees who will not always agree with them. Disagreement creates the best ideas and solves problems, creates positive relationships and promotes the employees' personal growth and development. The experience shows that in a stressful situation, the main life hack for a manager is to minimize desperate attempts to find the culprits in order to close the problem as soon as possible. Moreover, you do not need to focus all the blame on yourself. That is, it is worth taking time not to think about the culprits, but about further actions. It is necessary to analyse what happened and learn lessons for the future.

In order to achieve the most successful discussion of disagreements with the senior, here is a list of actions that employees are encouraged to take to succeed in discussions with the superiors:

- to provide clear statements, supporting them with facts;
- to provide a history of personal courage;

- to demonstrate a commitment to overall business success;
- to be honest and straightforward, do not be hypocritical;
- do not make the boss feel awkward;
- perceive the manager as a mentor.

Conflicts occur not only in the office, but also in the conditions of remote work. Let's consider how to resolve working conflicts during remote work with the lowest losses. The conflicts can take place because of differences in hardware, software and cases, messengers and data stores. Since when working together in a remote format it is necessary to use the same information tools, it is better to make a declarative decision.

Many managers with this work format have difficulty controlling employees. It is recommended to move to goal management and ensure maximum transparency. With online communications, relatively little information is obtained – only the upper body of the participants is visible, and sometimes the camera is completely turned off, which is an obstacle to reading many non-verbal signals. That is why it is recommended to use elements of active facilitation in meetings.

Conflicts can also arise among the employees who, taking advantage of the fact that they are far from their superiors, choose a more flexible schedule and spend less time at work. As a result, the work done loses quality, which causes dissatisfaction with the authorities. In this case, the manager should provide assistance to the employee, set clear tasks and determine the exact time frame for their implementation. In addition, during the conference, employees often start talking at the same time, which prevents them from analysing and structuring ideas and statements. In this case, the manager must organize the sequence of speeches.

An excellent solution is to divide the discussion into phases. This is a "brainstorming" technique, where there are the following stages: opinion expression, analysis, integration and decision-making. During each phase, the participants should do only one thing, i.e., voice their options for solving the problem (without evaluation) or share concerns (again, without general discussion). It is the integration phase that provides an opportunity to discuss and evaluate all voiced thoughts, ideas and risks. At the last stage, the participants vote for the options (taking into account the preliminary discussion) and make a general decision.

By following these phases and rules, all the participants remain in the context of what is happening, remain involved and do not engage in destructive conflicts, the final decision is made by all. This method of conducting online meetings takes more time, but the efficiency increases many times over. At remote work conflicts on the basis of delaying the communication are brightly found out. A loud rule of: "urgent question – call" can be enforced. In addition, it is possible to create a common task board, which shows what each employee is doing at the moment, as well as frequent online discussions.

Conflicts in remote work may be due to the fact that employees of companies involuntarily became available to superiors 24/7. That is, the prerequisites of work conflicts during remote work are poor management and differences in the views of team members on the work process etc.

Here's what one can do to improve the situation during remote communication and avoid destructive conflicts.

- to pay attention to insults;

If it is relatively easy to trace any obvious and not very non-verbal and verbal actions in life, then it is much more difficult in correspondence. All the participant can do is listen to the interlocutor's voice and intonation during the call or try to read emotions from the text. In order to eliminate the conflict, it is important to listen to everything that seems disrespectful.

- to use video calls;

Sometimes criticism in writing sounds too serious and frightening, but if you add a calm voice, gestures and a friendly mood, the opponents' nerves will be saved.

- criticism as early as possible;

It is much easier to criticize in the early stages of a project when there is an opportunity to correct something. If colleagues have not made public all the necessary information, then you should ask for it to find shortcomings in time.

It is worth being aware of what is happening in other teams. Especially when working in a large company. It may be worthwhile to introduce a general organizational call once or twice a for convenience.

This approach will avoid conflicts and misunderstandings at an early stage.

- to use emoji to show dissatisfaction.

The main thing is to agree with the team on the meaning of a particular symbol. For example, "skunk" can replace the phrase: "I have a bad feeling about this project".

Emoji look funny, soften the effect and slightly defuse the atmosphere before a serious conversation. And they are convenient to use when from the team of fast feedback.

In order to minimize reputational risk, it is proposed to use the following:

- creating an internal regulatory framework to eliminate conflicts of interest between employees and customers;
- strengthening the role of mission, values and corporate culture as a vector of communication and behaviour of company employees, the basis for implementing changes in business, building the brand;
- analysing the impact of reputational risk factors (both as a whole and individually) on performance indicators in general;
- reengineering the format of broadcasting the mission of values, tasks and achievements from the owner and management to employees, namely the channels and tools that make up the system of inner communication.

— the personnel segmentation and age and professional parameters base [7].

And after the end of conflict, it is necessary to draw conclusions and continue not to lead to destructive conflicts, maintaining tolerant, adequate and open relations with colleagues. It is not necessary to be toxic, to cross other people's personal borders, to call and demand involvement in work during non-working hours etc.

Diagnosing the conflict potential requires an urgent assessment of its strengths and weaknesses, finding the rational thought, compromise, alternative ways of resolving conflicts, and so on. The corporate responsibility strategy development, which includes investing in employees, and the concept of sustainable development will always be useful. In today's world, sustainable business development is the adaptation of managerial decisions, strategies and actions in order not only to meet the needs of the organization in profits, but also society to preserve nature, social security and the global economy. The growing concern for environmental and social issues obliges businesses to take responsibility and apply the principles of sustainable development to strategic management. The study of the conditions for improving the corporate sustainability effectiveness shows a significant dependence of sustainable business on the reputation and ethical behaviour of the company towards partners, consumers and competitors.

Conclusion

Conflict is inevitable in business, it stems from ideological, moral and ethical, reputational differences, as derivatives of the individual uniqueness. A moderate conflict is a healthy and necessary part of life of the organization. The optimal level of conflict in the team will maintain maximum productivity. The complete absence of conflicts in the group often indicates that people are hiding or simply holding back their opinion. But the leader needs to make sure that most conflicts are constructive. Destructive conflicts, of course, cannot be avoided due to the human factor, but the team leader's goal is to minimize them and compensate for the negative impact on the group as a whole by managing the conflict.

One of the main ways for maintaining a healthy condition of the conflict is to raise awareness among

the participants, i.e. to ensure that the conflict is about the subject and that the discussion should focus on it and not on the opponent's personality. In order to turn conflict into a positive one and for its resolution to contribute to the effective functioning of the team, the leader should clearly understand his/her role. In solving the issues connected with human behaviour and feelings, it is always necessary to show creativity and, most importantly, humanity. If the manager does not ignore the conflict situation, soon appears as a judge, lawyer, or one of the opponents. Therefore, we need knowledge, experience, solid competence in forecasting possible scenarios for defending our own point of view, protecting the interests of the enterprise, knowledge of the labour code, moral and ethical norms, personal and collective interests of each interested subordinate and business partners [8].

In the case of an online conflict, the best option is to switch to real contact (offline meeting, video) in order to increase empathy, facilitation and emotional connection, because this is one of the main causes of conflict in remote work. Another reason is lack or disruption of communication. In addition to the fact that transparent and open discussion can reveal useful details, it can be an element of team building.

Today, it is fashionable to think about the ease of creating start-ups, having heard that successful companies start in garages. Of course, it is possible to inspire a team, but the first mistake, and understanding such components as the abilities evaluation, empathy cards, Fishbone Diagram, reputation strategy, goal-setting SMART comes with experience. Every employee must understand his/her value, have the right to create and think and live at his/her own discretion, and be confident that in a difficult situation he will be heard and supported by superiors and colleagues. And if necessary, they will criticize the case and introduce a number of measures to eliminate the disunity of colleagues and managers. It is also important to avoid toxic workers during the selection phase, which will significantly reduce the concentration of destructive conflicts since their formation and increase the effectiveness of teamwork. Effective conflict prevention increases the company business reputation, helps to close gaps in administrative management, frees up time for team growth and development.

Abstract

Abstract. Conflict in business is inevitable, it stems from ideological, moral and ethical, reputational differences, as derivatives of the uniqueness of the individual. But confrontation in the form of a conflict of ideas, a conflict of available resources, or even personal conflicts can lead to the success or failure of teamwork. This will depend on how well the team is able to overcome these conflicts, how the team leader is able to diagnose the conflict, and how useful joint action will be to mitigate or avoid conflict.

The article pays special attention to topical issues of research and improvement of the conflict management system in the organization, discusses in detail the causes and consequences of conflicts within the team, ways to resolve and manage them. The aim of the article is to analyse how conflict can both help and harm the performance of the team, identify the causes of conflicts within the organization and ways to overcome and manage them. The main types of conflicts, their advantages and disadvantages are identified, the options of development and impact on the level of productivity of the group are investigated. A number of algorithms for

action in a conflict situation are also proposed, depending on the position held. Possible roles of team leader and conflict styles are analyzed. Ethical and psychological and reputational norms of team members' interaction in remote work are considered and real techniques and rules are offered to help achieve harmonious work remotely, because conflict can lead to finding new ideas and mechanisms for solving organizational problems, thus stimulating innovation and positive change. How to direct the conflict in the direction of cooperation and increase the efficiency of the team is considered. The issues explored in the article will help to acquire skills of structuring complex issues in conflict management.

A list of proposals that will increase the efficiency of activities and justify ways to de-escalate conflicts in offline and online modes. The methodological aspects of conflict management in the organization have been improved, measures to effectively prevent conflicts and eliminate gaps in administrative management have been proposed, which will increase the company's business reputation and serve as an additional reserve for team growth and development. A study of the influence of selected factors on the frequency of conflicts in the organization. Conclusions are formulated on the existence and main causes of conflict situations, among which are highlighted, in particular, the socio-psychological climate in the team, unresolved dispute resolution and unfair distribution of privileges. The value of solving this scientific problem is that the diagnosis of escalating conflicts will allow management to develop a set of preventive measures that are effective in preventing or smoothing out conflict situations.

Список літератури:

1. Алексейцев І.С., Галиахметов Р.М. Вирішення конфліктів та особливості національної ментальності // Соціосфера, 2020. № 2. С. 9-12.
2. Marylin KellyKelly, M.S. (2006). *Communication at work: Ethical, effective, i expressive communication в workplace*. Boston: Pearson.
3. Adler, R.B., & Rodman, G. (2018). *Understanding human communication (10th ed.)*. New York: Oxford University Press.
4. Putnam, L.L., & Wilson, C.E. (1982). Communicative strategies in organizational conflicts: Reliability and validity of measurement scale, в М. Burgoon (Ed.), *Communication yearbook 6* (pp. 629-652). Beverly Hills, CA: Sage.
5. Болтон, Р. (1979). *Вміння працювати з людьми: як заявити про себе, слухати інших та вирішувати конфлікти*. Енглвуд Кліффс, Нью-Джерсі: Прентіс-Хілл.
6. Рахім, М.А., Антоніоні, Д., та Псенічка, К. (2020). Модель структурних рівнянь влади лідера, стилів вирішення конфліктів підлеглими та продуктивності праці. *Міжнародний журнал управління конфліктами*, 12 (3), 191-211.
7. Current developments in management of human resources / V. Zamlynskyi, A. Livynskiy, I. Zakharkiv, T. Korneeva // *Knowledge management competence for achieving competitive advantage of professional growth and development: Collective monograph*. – Riga: BA School of Business and Finance, 2021. – P. 252-265. <http://dspace.kntu.kr.ua/jspui/handle/123456789/10569>.
8. Zamlynskyi, V., Domuschi, V., & Adil Mohamed Abdalla Sultan Al Ali. (2021). The importance of making the right management decisions in modern conditions of sustainable development. *Збірник наукових праць ЛОГОΣ*. <https://doi.org/10.36074/logos-29.10.2021.v1.10>.
9. V. Zamlynskyi, O. Stanislavyk, O. Halytskyi, M. Korzh, N. Reznik. Conflict Dynamic Model of Innovative Development in the System of Ensuring Competitiveness of an Enterprises, *International Journal of Scientific & Technology research*, Vol.9, issue 2, pp. 5322-5325, 2020. Режим доступу: <http://www.ijstr.org/final-print/feb2020/Conflict-Dynamic-Model-Of-Innovative-Development-In-The-System-Of-Ensuring-The-Competitiveness-Of-An-Enterprises.pdf>.

References:

1. Alekseitsev, I.S., & Haliakhmetov, R.M. (2020). Conflict resolution and the national mentality features. *Sotsiosfera*, 2. 9-12 [in Ukrainian].
2. Marylin KellyKelly, M.S. (2006). *Communication at work: Ethical, effective, i expressive communication в workplace*. Boston: Pearson.
3. Adler, R.B., & Rodman, G. (2018). *Understanding human communication (10th ed.)*. New York: Oxford University Press.
4. Putnam, L.L., & Wilson, C.E. (1982). Communicative strategies in organizational conflicts: Reliability and validity of measurement scale, в М. Burgoon (Ed.), *Communication yearbook 6* (pp. 629-652). Beverly Hills, CA: Sage.
5. Bolton, R. (1979). *Vminnia pratsiuvaty z liudmy: yak zaiavyty pro sebe, slukhaty inshykh ta vyrishuvaty konflikty (Ability to work with people: how to express yourself, listen to others and resolve conflicts)*. Englewood Cliffs, New Jersey: Prentis-Hill [in Ukrainian].
6. Rahim, M. A., Antonioni, D., & Psenicka, C. (2020). Model strukturnykh rivnian vlady lidera, styliv vyrishennia konfliktiv pidlehlmy ta produktyvnosti pratsi). *International Journal of Conflict*

- Management (Model of structural equations of a leader's power, conflict decision styles by subordinates and labor productivity), 12 (3), 191-211 [in Ukrainian].
7. Zamlynskyi, V., Livynskyi, A., Zakharkiv, I., & Korneeva, T. (2021). Current developments in management of human resources. Knowledge management competence for achieving competitive advantage of professional growth and development: Collective monograph. Riga: BA School of Business and Finance, 252-265. Retrieved from <http://dspace.kntu.kr.ua/jspui/handle/123456789/10569>.
 8. Zamlynskyi, V., Domuschi, V., & Adil Mohamed Abdalla Sultan Al Ali. (2021). The importance of making the right management decisions in modern conditions of sustainable development. Collection of scientific works ΛΟΓΟΣ. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.36074/logos-29.10.2021.v1.10>.
 9. Zamlynskyi, V., Stanislavik, O., Halytskyi, O., Korzh, M., & Reznik, N. (2020). Conflict Dynamic Model of Innovative Development in the System of Ensuring Competitiveness of an Enterprises, International Journal of Scientific & Technology research, Vol.9, issue 2, pp. 5322-5325. Retrieved from: <http://www.ijstr.org/final-print/feb2020/Conflict-Dynamic-Model-Of-Innovative-Development-In-The-System-Of-Ensuring-The-Competitiveness-Of-An-Enterprises.pdf>.

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